

under laboratory and upland field conditions in four replications.

Laboratory tests were performed according to International Seed Testing Association (1976) rules.

Hot water treatment at 52° C for 15 or 30 min or 57° C for 15 min did not damage seed quality when the seed was not presoaked (see table). Hot water at 52° C for 15 min actually improved field seedling vigor. Treatment at 57° C for 30 min significantly reduced seed quality, with further reduction when the seed was presoaked. Water temperature interacts with the length of hot water exposure, affecting viability.

Hot water-treated seed is seldom planted immediately after treatment. To determine whether hot water-treated seed deteriorates more rapidly over time, seed quality was evaluated after storage for 45 d. Seed quality deteriorated after storage under cool conditions (19° C at 50% relative humidity [RH]) and room temperature conditions (24-32° C and 78% RH). Room-stored seed was more severely affected, especially when treated at 57° C for 30 min.

Seed which was not presoaked tended to maintain viability and field emergence performance scores when subjected to regimes of 52° C for 15 and 30 min and 57° C for 15 min (see table). However, presoaked seed maintained viability and field emergence performance only with the 52° C for 15 and for 30 min regimes. The four cultivars followed a similar trend in response to the hot water treatments but showed some differences

Hot water treatment combinations observed to be safe for application to rice seed. IRRI.

	Hot water treatments ^a			
	52° C		57° C	
	15 min	30 min	15 min	30 min
Testing immediately after hot water treatment				
Seed presoaked for 3 h				
Standard germination test	+	+	+	-
Accelerated aging test	+	+	+	-
Field seedling emergence	+	+	+	-
Field seedling emergence rate	+	+	-	-
Field seedling vigor and morphological characters	++	+	+	-
Seed not presoaked				
Standard germination test	+	+	+	-
Accelerated aging test	+	+	+	-
Field seedling emergence	+	+	+	-
Field seedling emergence rate	+	+	+	-
Field seedling vigor and morphological characters	++	+	+	-
Testing after hot water treatment and 45 d storage				
Seed presoaked for 3 h				
Standard germination test	+	-	-	-
Accelerated aging test	+	+	-	-
Field seedling emergence	+	+	-	-
Field seedling emergence rate	+	+	-	-
Field seedling vigor and morphological characters	++	+	+	-
Seed not presoaked				
Standard germination test	+	+	+	-
Accelerated aging test	+	+	-	-
Field seedling emergence	+	+	+	-
Field seedling emergence rate	+	+	+	-
Field seedling vigor and morphological characters	++	+	+	-

^a + = statistically significant score reductions not observed i.e., safe treatment. ++ = scores significantly improved by the hot water treatment. - = scores significantly reduced by hot water treatment (unsafe treatment).

in vigor.

Hot water treatment of 57° C for 30 min may be considered unsafe for rice seed; the 57° C for 15 min may be considered safe only if the seed is not

presoaked before hot water treatment.

The 52° C for 15 and for 30 min treatments may be generally safe for rice seed, and are effective in controlling a range of seedborne pathogens. *S*

Genetic variability in 98 upland rice cultivars of India

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Genetic variability and extent of heritability of desirable traits were assessed in 98 upland rice cultivars sown in July 1983. Plots were 5 × 2 m in a randomized block design with 3 replications.

Range, mean, coefficients of variability, heritability, and genetic advance of 12 traits in 98 upland rice cultivars. Faizabad, India.

Trait	Range	Grand mean and SEM	GCV	PCV	ECV	Heritability (%)	Genetic advance (% of mean)
Seedling height (cm)	29.3- 67.0	51.9± 2.1	15.3	15.8	4.2	93.0	30.3
Days to 50% flowering	56.0- 99.0	77.6± 1.0	7.3	7.5	1.6	95.1	14.7
Culm angle	4.0- 27.0	12.3± 2.2	32.8	39.2	21.5	69.9	56.5
Leaf angle	9.2- 54.0	26.4± 2.4	26.7	29.0	11.4	84.5	50.4
Leaf length (cm)	31.1- 60.2	45.6± 2.9	8.9	11.9	7.9	56.2	13.7
Plant height (cm)	55.5-138.9	103.1± 3.0	14.4	14.9	3.6	94.3	28.9
Panicle length (cm)	17.4- 31.2	24.3± 1.1	9.4	10.8	5.4	75.2	16.7
Sheath length (cm)	15.8- 26.4	21.2± 1.1	6.8	9.4	6.4	52.5	10.2
Tillers/plant	5.4- 20.0	11.1± 3.1	19.5	39.3	34.1	24.7	20.0
Grains/panicle	66.0-405.6	139.0±24.3	30.7	37.5	21.4	67.3	52.0
Test weight (g)	10.4- 34.0	23.4± 1.0	15.9	16.8	5.2	90.5	31.3
Grain yield/plant (g)	5.9- 34.6	18.3± 3.2	17.2	27.7	21.7	4.0	22.1

All traits except length of sheath showed a wide range of phenotypic variation (see table). The phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV) was higher than the genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV). PCV ranged from 7.51 (days to 50% flowering) to 39.32 (tillers/plant). Culm angle, grains/panicle, leaf angle, and grain yield showed high GCV and PCV. The environmental coefficient of variability

(ECV) was higher for tillers/plant, yield/plant, culm angle, and grains/panicle, indicating that these traits were more susceptible to environmental factors than the other traits. Heritability ranged from 24.67 to 95.13%. High value for heritability was observed for days to flowering, plant height, 25-d-old seedling height, test weight, leaf angle, and panicle length. Low values were observed for

tillers/plant, grain yield, length of sheath, and length of leaf. The remaining traits showed moderate heritability.

Genetic advance in percent of mean was high for culm angle, grains/panicle, leaf angle, test weight, seedling height, and plant height. Selection for these traits might be more effective than for the other traits. $\mathcal{S}$

Metroglyph analysis of lowland rice cultivars

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Morphological variations in 44 lowland rice cultivars were studied using score index and metroglyph methods. Index values of range of variability were partitioned into 4 groups using class intervals (see table). All traits except

yield and plant height, are represented by rays on the glyph (the rays for the same trait have the same position on each glyph). The performance of a particular genotype is denoted by its index score (see figure). $\mathcal{S}$

Indices of rice traits.

Character	Range of means	Score 1 Value<	Score 2	Score 3	Score 4 Value>
Days to flowering	104.33-133.00	111.49	111.49-118.65	118.66-125.81	125.81
Internodes (no.)	4.27- 7.00	5.00	5.00- 5.500	5.51- 6.00	6.00
Tillers/plant	7.33- 25.60	11.89	11.89- 16.45	16.46- 21.01	21.01
Panicle length (cm)	22.43- 35.30	25.64	25.64- 28.85	28.86- 32.06	32.06
Grains/panicle	127.47-335.60	179.50	179.50-231.53	231.53-283.56	283.56
Kernel length (mm)	4.47- 8.00	5.35	5.35- 6.23	6.24- 7.11	7.11
Kernel breadth (mm)	1.50- 2.37	1.71	1.71- 1.92	1.83- 2.13	2.13
Test weight (g)	11.83- 35.67	17.79	17.79- 23.75	23.76- 29.71	29.71

Variability of pigment in lowland rices of Uttar Pradesh, India

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Pigments traits in 5 plant parts were identified in 44 lowland cultivars, using I.S.I. India color chart.

Of 33 pigments found, kernel (K) had 13, grain (G) 12, node (N) 9, internode (I) 7, and leaf (L) 4 (see table).

Serial numbers were assigned to pigments:

- | | |
|---------------------------|------------------------|
| 1 = eau-de-nil | 18 = dark stone |
| 2 = sea green | 19 = portland stone |
| 3 = grass green | 20 = vellum |
| 4 = sage green | 21 = light straw |
| 5 = light bronze green | 22 = light biscuit |
| 6 = middle bronze green | 23 = champagne green |
| 7 = light brunswick green | 24 = sunshine |
| 8 = cypress green | 25 = beige |
| 9 = light olive green | 26 = light brown |
| 10 = steel furniture | 27 = middle brown |
| 11 = forest green | 28 = nut brown |
| 12 = deep cream | 29 = golden brown |
| 13 = light buff | 30 = orange brown |
| 14 = middle buff | 31 = light salmon pink |
| 15 = deep buff | 32 = chocolate |
| 16 = light stone | 33 = service brown |

The broad variability of kinds and distribution of pigments could be used to document cultivars, in genetic studies, as marker traits, and to incorporate desirable traits in breeding programs. $\mathcal{S}$

Grain yield/plant (g)

Scatter diagram of metroglyph analysis. List of cultivars: 1. Adamchini, 2. Anandi, 3. Bansfool, 4. Bansfore, 5. Bhainslote, 6. Bhedkabra, 7. Bhatafool, 8. Brahma, 9. Dato, 10. Deharadon, 11. Derai, 12. Duniapat, 13. Foolbagan, 14. Gajraj, 15. Gauria A, 16. Gauria B, 17. Jilhore, 18. Kanakjiri, 19. Karinga, 20. Karingi, 21. Karanga, 22. Kesar, 23. Lakara, 24. Latera, 25. Lawangchur, 26. Lejura, 27. Madhukar, 28. Motibadam, 29. Ramkajara, 30. Rath, 31. Sahadeia, 32. Saro, 33. Selhi, 34. Sengar A, 35. Sengar B, 36. Silhat, 37. Shyamjira, 38. Sugapankhi A, 39. Sugapankhi B, 40. Sonachur, 41. Sorhi, 42. T-9, 43. T-100, and 44. Tulsifool.